

Forecasting with Pen, Paper and Ruler: Nomograms ahead!

a.k.a. as 'alignment chart' or 'abaque'

Introduction

- Prediction is important field in Machine Learning (ML)
- Normally computational task
- Computers are not useable everywhere
- Analog method required

Use Cases

- Medicine
- Public Health
- Agriculture
- Engineering

Working Principle

- Estimate relationships between exogenous variable(s) with one endogene variable
- draw a line between all exogenous variables.
- extend the line until the exogenous variable is reached
- read the value at the intersection point of the line the the scale
- use pynomo (Python) or rms (R).

Plot nomogram using Pynomo (Boulet et al., 2020), see also (Marasco et al., 2011)

In [41]:

```
import sys
from pynomo.nomographer import *
# unittiate three axis shown here:

N_params_1={
'u_min':0.0,
'u_max':10.0,
'function':lambda u:u,
'title':r'$X$',
'tick_levels':3,
'tick_text_levels':1}

N_params_2={
'u_min':0.1,
'u_max':12.0,
'function':lambda u:u,
'title':r'$Z$',
'tick_levels':3,
'tick_text_levels':1,
'scale_type':'linear smart'}

N_params_3={
'u_min':0.0,
'u_max':10.0,
'function':lambda u:u,
'title':r'$Y$',
'tick_levels':3,
'tick_text_levels':1}

# plotting parameters
# connects three dictionaries shown above

block_1_params={
'block_type':'type_2',
'width':10.0,
'height':10.0,
'f1_params':N_params_1,
'f2_params':N_params_2,
'f3_params':N_params_3,
'isopleth_values':[[9,1.5,'x']]
}

# appearence of the plot

main_params={
'filename':'nomogram_mult.pdf',
'paper_height':10.0,
'paper_width':10.0,
'block_params':[block_1_params],
'transformations':[('rotate',0.01),('scale paper',)],
'title_str':r'$X/Y=Z$',
'debug':False}

# eventual plot command (saves as pdf here)
Nomographer(main_params)
```

Out[41]:

<pynomo.nomographer.Nomographer at 0x27aade08d30>

A More Sophisticated Example using R

We assume a 20 years old, female person with a pclass=2 ticket

Task: predict her survival chance

Dataset 'titanic3' (Harrell Jr, 2015) provided from PASWR package (Arnholt, 2012)

Nomogram has been plotted using rms package (Harrell Jr, 2021)

Advantages

- no computer required
- suitable predictions in praxi
- unbiased average
- simplicity (one value output)
- no expert knowledge required (application)
- state of the art in medicine see (Zhang et al., 2021, p. 6) or (Li et al., 2021, p. 7)
- old technique see (Berl, 1935, p. 34)

Limitations

- computer needed for printing the Nomogram
- no error output
- no further inference
- ruler required
- no extrapolation
- axis bands often logarithmized
- axis resolution is crucial to draw correctly

Literature

Arnholt, A. T. (2012). PASWR: PROBABILITY and STATISTICS WITH R. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=PASWR> (<https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=PASWR>)

Berl, E. (Ed.). (1935). Chemische Ingenieur-Technik. Springer Berlin Heidelberg. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-90844-6> (<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-90844-6>)

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Li, Y., Zhang, J., Wang, B., Zhang, H., He, J., & Wang, K. (2021). A nomogram based on clinicopathological features and serological indicators predicting breast pathologic complete response of neoadjuvant chemotherapy in breast cancer. Scientific Reports, 11(1), 11348. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-91049-x> (<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-91049-x>)

Marasco, J., Doerfler, R., & Roschier, L. (2011). Doc, What Are My Chances? UMAP Journal, 32, 279–298.

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